

Design and Implementation of a Voice Controlled Robot with Obstacle Detection for Disabled People

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ABSTRACT

In this study, a robot has been designed and manufactured to perform voice commands. The goal of this robot is to help paralyzed people to do their daily tasks individually. The robot consists of an atmega8a microcontroller, a Bluetooth receiver module, a power unit, and a motor driver. An MLP neural network has been trained to classify the input voice into five different classes and the accuracy is 88.3% with a 2.3% variance. The trained network analyzes the input voice and the result of the ANN sent to the robot. The Bluetooth receiver module and the microcontroller receive the output data of ANN and turned into the commands for motor drive. The robot is going to move in the desired direction. It would be stopped by operator command or if there is an obstacle in the 10 centimeters in front of the robot which sensing it by ultrasound sensor.

Keywords: Robot, Microcontroller, Voice commands, Bluetooth, Disabled people

1. INTRODUCTION

Some injuries and illnesses disrupt normal human behavior in a way that can affect the quality of daily life and performance of the person. Due to impaired functioning, unable people are in constant need of other's help. This can bring mentally problems for the patient that it may cause to decrease the treatment quality and also find their life unpleasant, and it's also possible that these people need a nurse who can take care of them which in the long run can impose huge costs on the disabled person. If they can use machines and robots to do some of their daily tasks the problems mentioned may decrease over time and lead them to a better quality of life. Therefore, the design and manufacturing robots that meet such goals are becoming more considerable. Robots that can move based on patient commands are desirable for such issues. In addition, the usage of robots for normal people to facilitate their activities has been greatly welcomed in recent years. The design and fabrication of such robots are even on the agenda of governments and a large private company, they can take the lead in trading such new technologies with huge financial resources. Therefore, conducting research on robots and making different types of them can lead to advances in the field by creating a competitive environment. There have been many approaches to research on how robots are commanded. Robots which based on voice commands have always been interesting [1-3]. In this type of robots, certain commands will be defined, the software part can process and classify these commands and send an appropriate command to the robot to move [4-5]. To help disabled people, in addition to voice signal processing for wheelchair movement, signal processing such as EOG[6-7] or eye blinking[8] are used too. The usage of brain signal (EEG) as an exciting topic in

the control of robots has been extensively discussed in recent years entitled of Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCI) [9-12]. The purpose of this study is to design and build a robot that can execute commands and perform five different movements. There were some voice commands which have been processed in Matlab and classified into the five groups and then transfer to the robot as commands. The structure of the paper is as follows: first of all, the different part of the device has been introduced as a block diagram. Then the software and hardware have been described. Afterward, the protocol and details of voice recordings have been explained and finally, the process and condition of robot movement have been mentioned.

2. METHOD

The block diagram of the device is shown in figure1. The device has five main parts which include: voice command receiver unit, voice command processing, command transfer to robot unit, receiving units on the robot and the power unit.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of voice command transmitter and robot components

2.1 Voice command receiver unit

The voice command must first be obtained from the operator, Afterward, get processed and classified and eventually transferred to the robot as commands. Microphone Sony SM-888 was used to get voice commands from the user. Voice commands were recorded and converted to digital data on a computer with MATLAB software in an 8-bit format. The sampling rate in this software considered 4800 Hz. 100 command samples were recorded, each command takes 2 seconds to record.

2.2 Voice commands processing and classification unit

In the preprocessing step, the acoustic signal was filtered by a 5th order Butterworth band pass filter. The filter's low and high cutoff frequencies were considered as 70Hz and 280 Hz respectively. After the voice command is received by the computer, the processing part in MATLAB software classified the commands into five classes including Front

(F), Back (B), Left (L), Right (R) and Stop (S) [13]. The classification part has been done by the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) [14]. ANN needs to be trained by the data called training data in order to perform the classification properly. Before training the ANN, It is necessary to accurately design and pick the number of layers and neurons in each layer. The neural network used in this study is Multilayer Perceptron (MLP). Fourier transform of each acoustic signals with 480-samples per window with 25% overlap is applied to the neural network as input. The middle layer also called the hidden layer was considered as a layer with 10 neurons. The proper number of neurons in the hidden layer by means of table 1 obtained by testing several different network configurations with the different number of neurons in the hidden layers and the accuracy percentages of the ordered classifications in each arrangement. The number of neurons in the output layer is equal to the number of classes (commands), in this case, 5 neurons.

From 100 recorded samples, 70 samples for training, 15 samples for validation and 15 samples for neural network testing are given. For analysis, the 10-fold cross-validation method was used so the neural network with the mentioned structure was trained 10 times and the average accuracy was 88.3% with a 2.3% variance for the classification of commands. The network stopping condition was considered both the epoch number and the error criterion.

The first step in transferring the command to the robot is that after recording the command by MATLAB software, the trained network get ran and the received data to be classified. The neural network marks each received voice with the tag of one of the classes (commands). Then, the command has been diagnosed and prepared as a string label for subsequent command transfer steps.

Table. 1. Percentage of accuracy obtained from neurons change in the neural network hidden layer

	The number of hidden layer neurons	Average percentage accuracy of classification
ANN Structure	6	84.3 ± 3.8
	8	88.1 ± 2.9
	10	88.3 ± 2.3
	12	86.2 ± 3.2

2.3 Robot command transfer unit

The Bluetooth transmitter module installed on the PC hardware [15] then the neural network output (tag of the class) can be sent via the PC virtual serial port [16]. Since the Bluetooth receiver module was set to automatic mode, a virtual serial port in transmitter was adjusted to baud rate 9600.

2.4 Robot command receiver unit

Robot command receiver components include Bluetooth receiver module, microcontroller, and motor drive [17]. By turning on the Bluetooth receiver module on the robot, it can be paired with a Bluetooth designed sender module so the data can be transferred between them. Subsequently, the command class can be transfer from the processor to the robot hardware. The Bluetooth module has a voltage tolerance threshold of 1.8 V to 3.6 V and can withstand a current up to 50 mA. The Bluetooth module used is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Robot Bluetooth module

Through the Tx port of the Bluetooth receiver module, the command class is sent to the Rx port of the microcontroller. The microcontroller for this robot is Atmega8a (8-bit AVR microcontroller). The microcontroller is programmed by the Atmel Studio compiler, which uses the conditional instructions to identify the command class and convert it into a binary command. Then this command can be transferred to the robot motor driver. The following flowchart in figure 3 shows how the microcontroller acts facing the inputs.

Fig. 3. Robot's microcontroller flowchart.

Since the microcontroller output produces a voltage of 3.3 volts and a current of 40 mA, it is not capable of rotating the motor. Therefore the interface circuit must be used to connecting the microcontroller to the motor. These circuits are known as motor drivers, which consist of the power transistors in the form of integrated circuits. The motor driver used in this robot is 16 stand L293d.

2.5 Power unit

There are two types of regulators with constant voltage output were used to regulate the voltage of electrical components on the robot. One of the used regulators is LM7805 with 5V voltage which is intended to enable the motor drivers which shown in figure 4. The other regulator is the LF33, which is used for the Bluetooth receiver module and microcontroller's voltage regulation. This regulator has a regulated output voltage of 3.3 V. Also, a 12V battery was used to power the regulators and motor drivers.

Fig. 4. LM7805 Regulator power supply

The details of the microcontroller, motor drivers, the Bluetooth module and Ultrasound sensor is illustrated in figure 6.

3. RESULTS

After assembling the components and mounting the hardware on the robot chassis, the robot was launched with a 12V battery and a key. As the robot circuit getting activated, the Bluetooth module is not paired with the transmitter, which requires the user to scan the robot module by entering the desired code through the computer and the Bluetooth module on the hardware. By pairing the robot module with the Bluetooth transmitter module, the robot module monitor switches from the flashing frequency of 0.5 Hz to the frequency of 1 Hz, then the robot is ready to receive the direction code. For sending the direction code, the user loads the trained network into the MATLAB software, and the microphone gets ready to receive the user command by running the code. Then, the user was asked to perform the four basic directions by the microphone. By applying each movement command the robot moved with a constant speed to the desired direction, the robot got stopped by facing an obstacle in 10 centimeters by measuring the distance between the robot's front and obstacle with the ultrasound sensor. Also, if the robot did not face the above-mentioned condition, it would be stopped by voice command by the robot user according to the algorithm mentioned above. The robot hardware components are shown in figure 5.

Fig. 5. The robot's outward with the hardware component

It is worthwhile to mention that the database for training networks was gathered by 5 different people and the robot answered well to all the voice commands. Also for an easier way to switch between the users a database was designed and coded into MATLAB software for choosing the right trained network for each person.

Fig. 6. Robot Hardware Components circuit schematic

4. CONCLUSION

In this study, a useful robot was designed and fabricated being able to move in different directions based on voice commands using ANN classifier. One of the most important reasons for nursing people with disabilities is their inability to do their daily routine tasks due to lack of access to important parts of their house or inability to reach the vehicle. But most of these patients usually have the ability to speak and pronounce the words correctly. To help these patients, using a smart system based on voice commands can meet the needs of a large number of these patients. The recording voices get processed and after classification sent the commands via Bluetooth to the robot. The microcontroller of the robot processed the input data and transfer it to motor drivers. Then the robot is going to move in the desired direction. There is an ultrasound sensor in order to interrupt the robot movement if there is an obstacle nearly 10 centimeters of the robot. This robot has been trained by 5 different voices and the ANN result was nearly 88.3%. There is an option to gather more data for training in order to generalize the robot. It is also possible to provide more instruction for the robot by upgrading the robot hardware, and using more sensors and installing mechanical-electronic facilities. Depending on the person's disability or level of disability, other critical signals such as EMG, EOG, or EEG can also be used to deliver commands to the robot that require complex processing instruments and precise algorithms.

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